

Interaction of Aromatic Amines and Dithiazolidines: Formation of *N*-(Disubstituted formamidino)-*N'*- substituted Thiocarbamides and their Oxidation

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3,5-Diaryl (or alkylaryl)-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines on being allowed to react with aromatic primary amines afford the related *N*-(diarylformamidino)-*N'*-aryl or alkyl thiocarbamides. The 5-methylphenylamino- and 5-ethylphenylamino-3-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolines, both with aniline, however, afford one and the same product, the *N*-(diphenylformamidino)-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide. The formamidinothiocarbamides, so obtained, on oxidation undergo ring closure to appropriately substituted 1,2,4-thiadiazolidines.

In continuation of the earlier work¹, the interaction of aromatic amines and 3,5-diaryl (or alkylaryl)-imino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines (I) has been found to afford the related *N*-(diarylformamidino)-*N'*-aryl or-alkyl thiocarbamides (II), the identity of which has been confirmed by preparation from the related *NN'*-diarylguanidines and aryl or alkyl isothiocyanates².

Similar reaction of aromatic amines with 5-methylphenylamino- and 5-ethylphenylamino-3-phenylimino-1,2,4-dithiazolines (III), however, affords not the expected products but, in both cases, *N*-(diphenylformamidino)-*N'*-phenylthiocarbamide (IV) which has been found identical with the condensation product of diphenylguanidine and phenyl isothiocyanate. The identical product can arise from different dithiazolines (III) only by the replacement of any one of the sulphur atoms and the alkylamino group by an anilino group. Thus:

1. Dixit, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 151; 1961, **38**, 221.
2. Kurzer and Sanderson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 3240; Suresh, Ph. D. Thesis, 1960, Banaras Hindu University.
3. Cf. Fromm and Baumhauer, *Annalen*, 1968, **361**, 319.

TABLE I

No.	Reactants:	Thiocarbamate: M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.	1,2,4-Thiazolidinone. M.P.	Formula.	Found.	Calc.	
	1,2,4-Dithiazolidine and aniline.									
1.	3,5-Diphenylimino- and anilino	164°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	C: 60.13% H: 5.32 N: 13.96	99.36 5.20 16.18	**122° (230°)	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₄ S, HBr	Equiv.: 421	425	
2.	3,5-Di- <i>p</i> -tolylimino- and <i>p</i> -toluidine	154°	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	N: 14.82	14.07	294° (226°)	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ S, HBr	C: 59.06% H: 4.97 N: 11.78 **Equiv.: 464 (416)	59.10 4.92 11.99 467 (422.5)	
3.	3-Methylimino-5-phenylimino- and anilino	138-39°	C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ S	C: 63.36 H: 5.53 N: 19.58	63.38 5.43 19.71		212-13° (223°)	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₄ S, HBr	N: 15.13 **Equiv.: 360 (315)	15.42 363 (318.5)
4.	3-Methylimino-5- <i>p</i> -tolylimino- and <i>p</i> -toluidine	121°	C ₁₇ H ₂₀ N ₄ S	N: 17.56	17.94		231°	C ₁₇ H ₁₈ N ₄ S, HBr	C: 52.45 H: 4.67 N: 14.12 Equiv.: 393	52.17 4.85 14.32 391
†5.	3-Phenylimino-5-methylphenylamino- and anilino	185-86°	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₄ S	C: 60.0 H: 5.21 N: 15.85	69.38 5.36 16.18					
†6.	3-Phenylimino-5-ethylphenylamino- and aniline.	*164°	Do	Do	Do					

*Undepressed mixed m.p. with products (1) and (6).

**Refer to hydrogromies. M.p. and equiv. of the corresponding hydrochlorides are shown in parentheses.

†Kuzner and Sanderson's record m.p. 226-238°.

‡No. 5 and 6 refer to 1,2,4-dithiazoline.

TABLE II

S. No.	Reactants.	Product.	M.P.
1.	Diphenylguanidine and phenyl isothiocyanate	<i>N</i> -(Diphenylformamidino)- <i>N'</i> -phenylthiocarbamide	165.66°
2.	Di- <i>p</i> -tolylguanidine and <i>p</i> -tolylisothiocyanate	<i>N</i> -(Di- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino)- <i>N'</i> - <i>p</i> -tolylthiocarbamide-	154.55°
3.	Diphenylguanidine and methyl isothiocyanate	<i>N</i> -(Diphenylformamidino)- <i>N'</i> -methylthiocarbamide	130°
4.	Di- <i>p</i> -tolylguanidine and methyl isothiocyanate	<i>N</i> -(Di- <i>p</i> -tolylformamidino)- <i>N'</i> -methylthiocarbamide	120°

Sincere thanks of the author are due to Dr. R. H. Sahasrabudhey for his keen interest, to Prof. G. B. Singh, and the authorities of Banaras Hindu University for facilities, and to the Ministry of Scientific Research and Cultural Affairs, Government of India, for a scholarship.

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Received August 7, 1962.